

IMPROVING THE PROCESSES OF STRATEGIC ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL PRODUCTS

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Abstract. *In the implementation of marketing analysis in tourist enterprises, it is considered to study the market, to have high-quality and accurate information about competitors in the market, to use marketing information in the tourist-hotel business, to process them and bring them into the necessary form.*

Keywords: *Tourist enterprise, market, competition, business, information.*

СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПРОЦЕССОВ СТРАТЕГИЧЕСКОГО АНАЛИЗА РЫНКА ТУРИСТИЧЕСКО-РЕКРЕАЦИОННЫХ ПРОДУКТОВ

Аннотация. *При осуществлении маркетингового анализа в туристских предприятиях принято изучать рынок, располагать качественной и достоверной информацией о конкурентах на рынке, использовать маркетинговую информацию в туристско-гостиничном бизнесе, обрабатывать ее и доводить до необходимой форму.*

Ключевые слова: *туристское предприятие, рынок, конкуренция, бизнес, информация.*

One of the main components of the market mechanism is competition. A market economy requires the existence of competition, regardless of its maturity level and development characteristics. At the same time, with the development of the market economy, competitive relations are improving and changing their forms. Competition between independent producers of goods (enterprises) is a struggle to produce goods under favorable conditions and to sell them at a price that brings good profit, to strengthen their position in the economy as a whole. In doing so, they struggle to purchase the necessary means of production, raw materials, and hire labor. Competition between manufacturers ultimately means a struggle to attract consumers.

60.8% indicated the main problems of the travel agency's activity: high competition in the market of tourist services, insufficient state support for tourism development - 55.0%, lack of own funds - 51.7%, consumers' inability to pay - 49%.

The importance of the problems is presented by companies operating in the tourist market for different periods of time. Firms that have been operating for less than a year face the strongest competition. Firms that have been in business for more than five years put this problem in the fourth place, while young firms are less confident of government support, while self-confident firms put this problem in the second place of importance.

In marketing, competitors are related to each other by their competitive strategies. Such a system of views has advantages for success in achieving the goal in the activities of the firms. According to F. Kotler, private firms in the market have four roles in the competitive struggle:

- 1) leader (40% of the market);
- 2) contender for leadership (30% of the market);
- 3) follower (up to 20% of the market);
- 4) buried in the "depths" of the market (up to 10% of the market).

The most important thing is to have information about competitors, new products and services. Because it is possible to quickly see the part of the market that belongs to the enterprise. In the analysis of competitors, as a rule, the study of competitors is carried out after the study of the market and the main competitors. Studying competitors allows you to know their strengths and weaknesses and determine in advance what strategies will be more effective. Collecting all the necessary information in the study of competitors is almost impossible in practice.

When conducting marketing analysis in tourist enterprises, it is important to study the market first. Having high-quality and accurate information about competitors on the market determines how the company will achieve competitive results.

The first group of information about competitors can include:

- 1) Proper organization of management;
- 2) Personnel resource;
- 3) Assets;
- 4) The possibility of receiving funds from other sources;
- 5) Realization volume;
- 6) Market share;
- 7) Profitability;
- 8) Management;
- 9) List of main services rendered;
- 10) Accuracy of information (for example, prices, costs for advertising, etc.).

The following can be added to the data of the second group:

- 1) Status of competitors;
- 2) Enterprise image, authority;
- 3) Qualification of management personnel;
- 4) Main goals;
- 5) Flexibility of marketing strategy;
- 6) Effectiveness of the product strategy.

Tourist companies try to reasonably prove that there are risks or favorable opportunities arising from the activities of competitors. This allows to assess the expected impact of competitors' actions on the state of the firm's operations and the potential of competitors, to estimate the remaining time reserve to perform the necessary actions.

The use of marketing information in the tourism-hotel business is related to their processing and transformation.

Figure 1. The role of comprehensive market analysis and marketing research in marketing activities.

The methods of working with them differ depending on the type of information. Marketing data collection sources can be conditionally divided into primary and secondary types. Primary data includes data and information created for the first time for a specific purpose. Secondary information includes information originally collected for other purposes, processed, available in various sources (journals, reports, newsletters, etc.). Primary data collection is carried out by specialized research firms, thus providing very valuable information for market firms. In addition, the tourist company will not need to conduct special marketing research every time. For this reason, the use of secondary information is effective in most tourism companies.

Sources of secondary data collection are divided into internal and external types, depending on whether or not they are relevant to the organization concerned.

Internal secondary data sources includes the indicators reflected in the current accounting, financial and statistical reports maintained by the organization. Including profit and loss, buying and selling, inventory, customer scope and location, price calculations, etc. To analyze such information in the tourist business, it is necessary to solve the problem of obtaining the necessary information from competitors. Therefore, it is considered appropriate to organize marketing research by regional tourist authorities.

In other words, the organization independently develops an internal information system, relying on the reports and data at its disposal. In practice, the organization determines the volume of products sold in natural and value measurement units, price changes during the year, location map of customers, changes in product stocks, and similar important information directly based on its internal reporting system.

Enterprise economic activity is characterized by the following quantitative indicators:

- * absolute amount and value of product (service) sales in the past, present and expected period;
- * costs and profits, production volume, production capacity, labor cost, productivity;
- * organization of sales, product movement directions;

- * information about types of sales, advertising costs, delivery time, price, contract and other conditions;

- * personnel, labor organization and management structure, distribution of tasks, possibilities of replacing senior positions, number of workers and employees;

External secondary data includes information available on the market, product, in which the organization operates or is expected to operate. Their composition in practice has different significance in the experience of different countries. For example, in developing countries, external secondary data can generally be divided into the following 4 groups.

1. Reports and bulletins of public and economic associations. These sources are divided into two subgroups according to their nature.

- A) Official reports of state institutions. These include statistical annals, reviews, etc. You can get information about population growth, structural demographic changes, income and price changes, gross consumption situation, supply of certain consumer goods, sellers, consumer news and other information from sources of this category.

- B) Reports and information of associations and organizations. Since each state has its own independent economic associations, they also prepare annual reports and data independently.

2. Information, reports of institutions specialized in marketing research and institutions providing marketing services.

In many cases, this source of information is also called a source of commercial information.

3. Economic press, industry magazines, newspapers and books. This category is a very broad source of information, and the analytical information contained in it can be related to an organization, a group of researchers, or an individual.

4. Publicly published information from organizations includes annual balance sheets, price lists, advertising magazines, buyer's guides, and the like. Such resources are also widely used by competing firms. Because, it will be possible to get the necessary information about the sales volume, product, service and price policy of competing companies.

In the marketing program, socio-economic information affecting the activity of the tourist enterprise includes:

- * demographic, social, political, economic trends;
- * composition of consumer savings, income and expenses of the population and enterprises;

- * general dynamics of prices, foreign trade;
- * the government's policy in the field of taxes, conditions for the development, control and regulation of economic activity;

- * various changes in legislation;

- * includes basic information on the flow of tourists and more.

Another research product should be included in the term secondary information - it is the use of surveys conducted by other tourist organizations. For example, according to the results of a survey conducted in the cities of Tashkent, Khiva and Bukhara in 2021, the following information was obtained about the tourist opportunities of Uzbekistan:

1. The seasonality factor affects the level of employment in accommodation and tourist enterprises of Uzbekistan less than expected.

2. Diversity and diversification are observed in the activities of most of the tourist enterprises.

3. Part-time employment in enterprises in the field is not as widespread as in European countries.
4. Our enterprises in the field are facing some difficulties in (finding) and selecting highly qualified personnel.
5. Various attitudes are expressed to the issue of personnel qualification improvement in placement enterprises; most employees acquire their skills directly on the job; to solve the issue of training abroad, from studying at the University to participation in short-term courses offered by private enterprises are considered; Internal training systems are not widespread in most of the hosting companies. The same situation is observed in tourist enterprises, in addition, the educational levels of their personnel in tourist enterprises are extremely different from each other, in which only some of the managers and technical staff have been trained abroad (outside the enterprise).
6. In the training of employees, first of all, learning a foreign language (especially English), using information technologies, technical skills needed at the workplace, using communication tools, learning etiquette, and gaining experience abroad (in other places) are required.
7. Employees are not required to have business skills (financial management, marketing, human resource management, quality management, etc.).

This information will help to identify common situations in tourism companies. In addition, the materials published by the Uzbektuizm MK every year are considered the most reliable secondary information.

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